

MICROHOLE MACHINING ON PRECISION CFRP COMPONENTS USING ELECTRICAL DISCHARGING MACHINING

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ABSTRACT

Recently CFRP has been focused in a variety of new applications such as precision electrical components, surgical tools and biomedical devices because of its light-weight and excellent mechanical property. However, the form accuracies of the mechanical features generated by traditional CFRP fabrication methods are limited to meet the requirements of microcomponents. Furthermore, due to the difficulties in mechanical machining of CFRP in microscale, sometimes alternative material removal method is required in production of precision devices. Micro-electrical discharge machining (EDM) has been used for manufacturing of microholes and 3D micromolds of metal workpieces because of its machining accuracy and non-contact machining characteristics. In this study, we have implemented micro-EDM to the precision machining of CFRP substrates that are also a conductor. Proper EDM conditions for microhole drilling of CFRP for precision component fabrication with micro features were studied. Experiments on micro-EDM machinability were performed using a commercial micro-EDM tool. A variety of machining parameters were tried such as open circuit voltage and maximum current. Material removal rate (MRR) and tool wear ratio (TWR) were compared with respect to experimental conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is frequently used composite material for light-weight design of products. Recently the application of CFRP has been extended to small and precise components because of its excellent mechanical properties. For example, CFRP has been used in microrobot flight components such as bending actuator and hinge locking components [1]. In electronic industry CFRP is considered to be applied for weight reduction of components such as shutter chamber and touchpad.

Drilling process is most frequently used machining process for CFRP. Compared to the machining of metals precise machining of CFRP is difficult due to severe tool wear, delamination and uncut fibers [2, 3]. Delamination of machined CFRP hole is one of the frequently occurred defects that deteriorates the surface quality. It is affected by drill bit geometry and thrust force from drilling processes. A variety of methods has been proposed to improve the quality of drilled CFRP surfaces: grinding drilling, vibration-assisted twist drilling and high speed drilling. Specially designed tools and support plate were also proposed. Abrasive water jet (AWJ) and laser machining are also used as alternatives for drilling. AWJ has fast machining speed, but, it generates tapered holes. AWJ causes delamination due to high velocity impact of the jet [4]. Laser machining also has fast speed, but, it

does not completely eliminate heat-affected zone (HAZ) on the machined surface [4]. Especially, laser machining is not effective to make deep microholes.

Recently, demands for drilling microhole on CFRP have been increased. In aerospace industry, microholes on nacelle are used to develop laminar flow to reduce fuel consumption [5]. Similar to the macro-scale drilling avoidance of defects, such as delamination and uncut fibers in microhole drilling, is important.

Electrical discharging machining (EDM), that is widely applied to fabricate micro metal structures, has been applied to machine CFRP microholes with high surface quality. Relationship between discharge current and surface quality was investigated to test the feasibility of EDM of CFRP [6]. Effect of pulse-on-time on material removal rate was investigated [7]. A method to drill better holes in CFRP by applying electrical discharge was developed. It was demonstrated that the electric discharge between drill and CFRP plate reduced the delamination [8]. A study on microhole machining on CFRP using micro-EDM process was presented. Variables influencing electrode wear, material removal rate and surface quality in micromachining were studied [9].

In this study machining characteristics of CFRP using micro-EDM were compared to that of metal utilizing single discharge experiment. Removal mechanisms of epoxy resin and carbon fibers were investigated experimentally. Blind holes were fabricated on CFRP in order to investigate the effects of machining parameters (e.g., maximum discharge current, open circuit voltage, pulse frequency and pulse duration time) on material removal rate (MRR) and tool wear ratio (TWR).

2 EDM CHARACTERISTICS OF CFRP

CFRP has unique EDM characteristics because it is composed of carbon fibers and epoxy resin that have different thermal properties. Experiments have been conducted to investigate the process characteristics when CFRP was machined by micro-EDM. Fig. 1 compares the scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the single discharge craters generated on metal (SUS304) and uni-directional CFRP (USN 125, SK Chemicals) surfaces. The machining experiment was conducted using a micro-EDM machine (SX-200-HPM, Sarix). As can be seen in the figure, a circular crater was generated on metal surface because the thermal energy was transferred uniformly due to its isotropic characteristic of metal. However, in case of machining uni-directional CFRP epoxy resin (melting temperature: 491 K) around the discharge spot was melted down and volatilized easily. Carbon fibers were only partially removed by a single discharge due to its high melting temperature (3,500 K). An elliptical crater is generated on the CFRP surface along the fiber direction owing to the higher thermal conductivity of carbon fiber ($8 \sim 70 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$).

In order to figure out material removal in carbon fiber portion by a single discharge few strands of carbon fibers were detached from CFRP and then machined using EDM. As can be seen in Fig 2, the carbon fiber was shorten about $10 \mu\text{m}$ by a single discharge and the end of the fiber was swollen. The coefficient of transverse expansion of carbon fiber is about $5.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The spark temperature of a few thousand degrees Kelvin during the EDM generates a transverse strain. The strain results in a swelling deformation of end of carbon fiber after micro-EDM [5].

These experimental results demonstrated that the proper selection of the EDM conditions is important because the excessive removal of epoxy resin deteriorates the machining accuracy. The excessive electrical power used in micro-EDM causes the smeared epoxy resin at the inlet of microholes. On the other hand, if the electrical power is too small the productivity is limited because the material removal rate of the fiber is low. Therefore, the value of machining parameter must be selected to maximize machining speed and to minimize resin damage around the hole.

Figure 1: Single discharge crater of (a) metal and (b) CFRP

Figure 2: A carbon fiber (a) before and (b) after single discharge applied.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

A series of experiments to machine blind holes on CFRP has been conducted to investigate relation of machining parameters and machining performance. Machining performance was evaluated by MRR and TWR, and the damage to the surface around the hole at inlet was also evaluated. Table 1 shows the parameters used in the experiment, such as maximum current, open circuit voltage, energy, pulse duration, and pulse frequency.

EDM parameter	Maximum current	Open circuit voltage	Energy*	Pulse duration	Pulse frequency
Symbol	I	V	SE	Ton	Freq
Unit	A	V	a.u.	μ s	kHz
Reference parameters	20	60	200	2.0	60

* Machine specific parameter used in Sarix EDM machine tool only

Table 1: Parameters of micro-EDM experiment.

A copper electrode with a diameter of 500 μ m was used to machine a blind hole with a depth of 250 μ m. TWR of electrode was examined because the tool wear during CFRP machining is significant. To figure out the wear of electrode a variety of maximum current, open circuit voltage, pulse duration, and pulse frequency values was applied. The energy parameter was fixed as SE number of 200. The EDM parameters examined in the experiments were maximum current (15 ~ 50 A), open circuit voltage (50 ~ 90 V), pulse duration (0.5 ~ 4 μ s) and frequency (60 ~ 120 kHz), respectively. Figure 3 shows TWR variation with respect to each parameter. To investigate the effect of each parameter the values of other parameters were fixed. Reference values for EDM parameters in Table 1 were experimentally determined that generates minimum damage at inlet without considering productivity. It has been proposed that to reduce the damage of machined hole lower values of maximum current

and open circuit voltage were required [9]. As can be seen in the figure, MRR was increased as maximum current increased, but, TWR was not increased after a maximum current exceeds 30 A. TWR was increased as open circuit voltage increased, but, MRR was not increased more than 0.012 mm³/min when open circuit voltage is greater than 80 V. MRR was increased by raising value of pulse duration, but, TWR was lowest when the duration was 2 μs. Pulse frequency did not affect MRR if the pulse frequency was not less than 75 kHz.

Figure 3: Tool wear ratio and material removal rate with respect to (a) maximum current, (b) open circuit voltage, (c) pulse duration and (d) pulse frequency

Damage of hole at inlet was investigated by varying the discharge energy of micro-EDM. As expected excessive discharge energy caused severe damage of hole at inlet by melting only epoxy resin. As a result carbon fiber was exposed at the top-surface. Figure 4 shows the damage of holes using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images when different discharge energies were applied. The maximum length of damaged fiber at inlet was about 464 μm in case of maximum open circuit voltage of 90 V was used.

Figure 4: Image of machined microholes: (a) hole with severe damage, (b) properly machined hole

Experiment was conducted to evaluate the machining performance with respect to energy level by varying the SE value. A copper electrode with a diameter of 500 μm was used to machine a blind hole with a depth of 100 μm . The maximum current, open circuit voltage, pulse duration, and pulse frequency are fixed at 15 A, 60 V, 2 μs and 60 kHz, respectively. As increasing the SE value from 114 to 265, the MRR and TWR were increased as shown in Fig 5. However, as expected, higher energy level resulted in more damage, especially, at the inlet of microholes. Figure 6 shows the SEM images of damaged hole at inlet. Epoxy resin was removed faster than carbon fiber relatively. As the energy level decreases, damage of microhole was remarkably reduced.

Figure 5: (a) Material removal rate and (b) tool wear ratio with sarix energy level.

Figure 6: Damage of inlet of microhole with sarix energy level (a) SE 265, (b) SE 200, and (c) SE 114

4 CONCLUSION

In this study we evaluated the process parameters of micro-EDM to investigate the characteristics of micro-hole drilling of CFRP. A single discharge craters on CFRP substrate and metal were compared. The elliptical crater in fiber direction was generated on uni-directional CFRP because of different thermal conductivity and melting temperature between carbon fiber and epoxy resin. The inlet damage of EDM drilled hole of CFRP was more severe than that of metal. The tool wear ratios with respect to a variety of parameters were evaluated. The maximum current, open circuit voltage, pulse duration, pulse frequency and discharge energy were examined. The experimental results suggest that the proper selection of process condition could increase the material removal rate and to decrease tool wear ratio of micro-EDM of CFRP.

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